

NATAE
North African Transition
to AgroEcology

CARI

21/11/2023

D5.2

Process Guidelines for MEDAE

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Glossary

Abbreviation	Full form
Administrative and Financial Manager	Person employed by the host organization, in charge of the network's administrative and financial follow-up.
Coordinator	Person employed by the coordinating organization, responsible for coordinating and leading network activities.
Coordinating organization	Organization responsible of the coordination and animation of network activities, who employs a coordinator
Annual meeting	Meeting with all network members to review the previous year, and share the strategic and operational vision for the year ahead.
Board	A body of member organizations sharing common objectives or specific features and entrusted with the same rights.
Focal point	Representative of one organization within the network
Host organization	Organization that hosts the network and employs an administrative and financial manager
MEDAE	MEDiterranean multiactor network on AgroEcology
Member	MEDAE network member organizations
Participant	People who join the network via their organization
Steering Committee	Decision-making body
Working group	A group of members interested in contributing to a specific area of network interest. Working groups are organized around a specific task or project. They are temporary and open-ended

Executive Summary

One of the objectives of the NATAE project is to create the MEDAE network (MEDiterranean multi-actor network on AgroEcology), a unique knowledge-sharing and capacity-building community on agroecology in the Mediterranean. By bringing together stakeholders from different types of institutions, disciplines, backgrounds and scales, the MEDAE network aims to bridge the gap between contexts, policies, local, national and international knowledge, and empirical and scientific know-how. It will stimulate exchanges and give a strong, unified voice to all stakeholders committed to the agroecological transition in the Mediterranean.

The MEDAE network will have no formal existence, at least during the first few years, but will operate according to the guidelines set out below. The guidelines comprise several sections detailing the network's objectives, membership, governance, activities, preferred modes of communication and economic model. These guidelines will be tested for 2 years, then reviewed and possibly adjusted in 2026.

Chapter 1

Introduction

Marion Comptour

Chapter 1 - Introduction

1. The MEDAE network

One of the key objectives of the NATAE project is to set up a network of stakeholders involved in agroecology in the Mediterranean: the MEDAE network (MEDiterranean multiactor network on AgroEcology). This network, set up during the NATAE project with the NATAE consortium, will gradually be extended to other interested organizations, with the ambition of continuing beyond the end of the NATAE project in 2026. The specificity of the MEDAE network, which stands out from other agro-ecology exchange networks, is that it focuses specifically on the Mediterranean zone, and brings together a wide range of stakeholders from this geographical area.

A network can be defined as "*an association of independent individuals or organizations, sharing a common goal or objective, within which members contribute resources and participate in exchanges, with a desire for reciprocity and collective benefit*" (Coordination Sud, 2016).

Depending on its objectives, the nature of its members and what they wish to share, a network takes different forms and adopts particular operating modes. Each network has an organization adapted to its characteristics: there are as many ways of operating as there are networks.

At least for the first few years, the MEDAE network will have no formal existence. However, its organization needs to be thought through, structured and approved by the parties involved. The aim of these guidelines is to set out the network's operating procedures.

**** Structural issues for guideline development ****

- What are the MEDAE network's objectives? What actions do we want to take? What do we want to share, bring to the network and get in return? What are our shared values?
- Which members do we want in the network? With whom do we want to exchange?
- More pragmatically, how can we get organized? What form of governance should be put in place to ensure that members are properly represented, and that management is efficient?
- How can we ensure the MEDAE network's continuity after the NATAE project, and in particular its funding?

These questions are addressed in the guidelines, which present in turn: the method used to prepare them, the network's objectives, its membership, its governance, its activities and the preferred methods of communication.

The guidelines will be reviewed in 2025, after the MEDAE network has been in operation for two years and may be readjusted in the final year of the NATAE project (2026), to take account of the lessons learned from the project and the prospects for network continuity.

2. Guidelines development:

This section describes the methodology adopted to draw up the MEDAE guidelines.

Within the NATAE consortium, CARI (Centre d'Actions et de Réalisations Internationales) was given responsibility for building the MEDAE network and drafting guidelines for its operation (Task 5.2), given its expertise in network coordination.

The guidelines were drawn up in stages over the course of 2023, using two main methods:

- A critical analysis of existing international networks;
- An interactive, collaborative process: the various members of the NATAE consortium were asked on several occasions to share their visions and expectations of the MEDAE network.

2.1 Critical analysis of international networks

Critical analysis of international networks has enabled us to draw lessons for MEDAE. This analysis is based on 3 main sources of information:

→ Synthesis studies on international networks

Several studies have shed light on the characteristics and functioning of international networks, the motivations for participating in networks, and the effects of networks on their members. A study conducted by Coordination Sud in 2016¹ was particularly useful. This study, carried out among several French NGOs, combined quantitative surveys with more qualitative case studies. It enabled us to identify 6 main types of international networks through 3 key criteria: (i) network objectives, (ii) levels of "integration" between network members (what is "shared" in the network), and (iii) the nature of the members.

→ An analysis of existing networks

Based on an analysis grid developed from the Coordination Sud study (2016), we reviewed the functioning (membership, governance, level of integration, communication tools, activities) of several existing networks² whose purpose is wholly or partly concerned with agroecology, and which act at different scales.

→ CARI's expertise

CARI is coordinator of several networks, including RADD0 (Réseau Associatif de Développement Durable des Oasis), RESAD (Réseau Sahel Désertification) and GTD (Groupe de Travail Désertification). He is also a member of several networks dealing with agroecology (Minka International), land conservation (Drynet), water resources (pS-Eau) and international solidarity (Coordination Sud, Occitanie Coopération...).

¹ Coordination sud is the national coordination network for French international solidarity NGOs. A 2016 study entitled "*Diversité d'appartenances aux réseaux internationaux: un changement d'échelle à la hauteur des finalités recherchées? Analyzing the experience of French NGOs*" analyzed how networks operate and how belonging to an international network helps strengthen members' capacity.

² Among others, we analyzed the following networks: Agroécologie Europe, Alliance pour l'Agroécologie en Afrique de l'Ouest (3AO), Coalition Agroécologie, Réseau Sahel Désertification (RESAD), Réseau associatif de Développement Durable des Oasis (RADD0), Minka International, Réseau des Initiatives Agroécologiques au Maroc (RIAM), Urgenci, Alliance for Food Sovereignty in Africa...

CARI has solid network expertise, consolidated by internal and external network assessments and capitalization work. We have drawn on this expertise to draw up these guidelines.

2.1.1 A collaborative process

The development of the guidelines is also based on a multi-stage collaborative process, during which the members of the NATAE consortium were able to present their expectations and suggest ways forward.

- **1st stage: Questionnaire**

A questionnaire (in English and French) was distributed in May 2023 to identify NATAE consortium members' expectations of the network (Appendix A. Questionnaire submitted to). The questionnaire covered: network experience, desired objectives for MEDAE, nature of membership, governance system, commitment, etc. The questionnaire was completed by 26 people, from 17 (out of 22) of NATAE's partner institutions. There was a good representation of the consortium's institutions (nature and geographical distribution). Of the 17 institutions that responded, 9 are located in Europe and 8 in North Africa.

Figure 1. NATAE partners who responded to the questionnaire

- **Stage 2: Discussion of a preliminary scenario on the MEDAE network launch day**

The critical analysis of existing networks and the responses to the questionnaire enabled CARI to draw up an initial scenario for the MEDAE network. This scenario was presented and discussed by the consortium at the MEDAE network launch day on July 4, 2023.

29 people attended this videoconference meeting, representing 17 partner institutions. Divided into 3 groups, the partners discussed the various options proposed (Appendix B. Preliminary scenario discussions).

The NATAE Advisory Committee was also invited, and some of its members took part in the discussions.

- **Stage 3: Drawing up guidelines: draft and final versions**

The discussions and proposals gathered during the network launch day enabled the scenario to be reworked and the guidelines to be drawn up. As opinions sometimes diverged, the options retained were validated by NATAE coordination (CIHEAM IAMM) during several working sessions with CARI. In September 2023, a provisional version of the guidelines was submitted to the consortium for comments and minor adjustments,

which will be discussed again with the coordinator. The final version of the guidelines will be submitted in December 2023.

- **4th stage (in 2025): evaluation during the course of the project**

MEDAE's operating mode will be reviewed in 2025, after two years of network activity. Adjustments may be made and tested in the last year of the NATAE project (2026), so that the operating mode is solid and approved when the NATAE project (and the funding dedicated to the network) comes to an end.

Figure 2. Guidelines development method

**** Key points: METHOD ****

- The guidelines for the operation of the MEDAE network are based on a critical analysis of existing international networks and on a co-construction process involving the entire NATAE consortium.
- These guidelines will be tested for two years and then rediscussed in 2025 in order to propose adjustments in the final year of the NATAE project.

Chapter 2

Network objectives and focus areas

Marion Comptour

Chapter 2 - Network objectives and focus areas

3. Main objectives

This section details the desired objectives for the MEDAE network: What will the network bring to its members? What needs will the network help to meet? What actions do members wish to carry out within the network? What will members share within MEDAE?

The MEDAE network has 3 general objectives, which will be broken down into specific objectives and concrete actions in a future network action plan.

Objective 1: Stimulate collaboration and projects between different stakeholders working to develop agroecology in the Mediterranean.

By bringing together stakeholders from different types of institutions³, disciplines, horizons and scales, the MEDAE network aims to bridge the gap between contexts, policies, local, national and international knowledge, and empirical and scientific knowledge. Different stakeholders will be able to work together towards a systemic and cross-sectoral understanding of agroecology. The network will foster international collaborations and encourage interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research approaches to agroecology. It will create a community of professionals and individuals committed to the agroecological transition in the Mediterranean.

Objective 2: Promote the exchange of information, knowledge, solutions and experience between network members.

The MEDAE network will stimulate exchanges between the various stakeholders involved in agroecology in the Mediterranean. Network members will be able to exchange information such as publications, funding opportunities, training and internship opportunities for students. They will also be able to share knowledge and experience, particularly of agroecological practices. These exchanges may take the form of webinars, workshops, question-and-answer sessions, panel discussions, case study presentations, etc.

The MEDAE network will thus act as a knowledge transfer accelerator, promoting peer-to-peer learning and capacity-building between different stakeholders.

Objective 3: Represent Mediterranean agroecology stakeholders at international level and develop political and scientific advocacy in favor of agroecology.

The MEDAE network will give a strong, unified voice to stakeholders committed to the agroecological transition in the Mediterranean. It will put into perspective the results achieved in the projects in order to pave the way for policymakers and developers. The MEDAE network will make it possible to advocate agroecology in the Mediterranean at local, national and international levels, and to represent Mediterranean agroecology stakeholders on the international stage.

It is important to note that being a member of the network does not mean being involved in all the network's productions, especially when it comes to advocacy. Thus, on the various advocacy documents produced, only

³ Research, education, technical institutes, development stakeholders, farmers, consumers, private companies...

the logos of organizations that agree with the message conveyed will be displayed. Focal points (Appendix G. Focal point roles) of the organizations will be responsible for requesting validation or not of their organization to be associated with the advocacy documents.

4. Area of interest

The MEDAE network focuses on agroecology in the Mediterranean. What is meant by Mediterranean? What are the network's boundaries for its activities (geographical, climatic, etc.)?

The countries of the Mediterranean basin share a common history, similar climatic and ecological characteristics and a natural heritage with a particularly rich biodiversity that must be preserved⁴ .

The climate, whether Mediterranean, semi-arid or arid, is characterized by high temperatures, low rainfall and marked drought.

From an agricultural point of view, the countries of the Mediterranean basin are characterized by emblematic productions (viticulture, livestock breeding, agro-pastoralism, arboriculture, oleiculture, date palm cultivation, market gardening, cereals and other field crops...), hosted within varied agroecosystems: cereal plains, valleys or irrigated plains, mountainous areas, peri-urban areas, and oasis and peri-oasis areas.

Mediterranean agriculture is facing a number of challenges, including exacerbated global warming⁵ with diminishing water resources, an increase in extreme weather phenomena, particularly drought, as well as soil artificialization and degradation, and heavy pressure on natural resources. Mediterranean agriculture is also impacted by strong demographic growth, an increase in the urban population, land pressure, and the high dependence of several countries on food imports. Against a backdrop of climate change and intensifying trade in goods and people, agricultural crops are also becoming increasingly vulnerable to pests and diseases.

While the agricultural programs of many Mediterranean countries still promote an industrial agricultural development model, agroecology is emerging as a holistic response to the challenges facing Mediterranean agriculture.

The MEDAE network aims to bring together organizations and individuals interested in agro-ecological transition(s) in the Mediterranean, to discuss and find solutions together to the ecological and socio-economic challenges facing Mediterranean agriculture. It is therefore important that the network's areas of interest are linked by similar challenges, enabling them to share experiences and solutions.

While numerous networks already exist on agro-ecology, the MEDAE network is unique in that it focuses on neighbouring Mediterranean countries that share the same major environmental, climatic and health challenges, while also having to meet the challenges of food security and nutrition.

We propose that the network's area of interest be set up in two stages, with a restricted area in the first phase, followed by an extension to include countries with similar agro-climatic conditions.

⁴ The Mediterranean basin is a biodiversity hot spot, characterized by a high level of plant diversity and endemism.

⁵ The Mediterranean is one of the regions most affected by climate change, with a sharp rise in temperatures and the frequency and intensity of droughts.

Phase 1: at least during the first year of the network (2024)

"Agroecology as practiced in African countries hosting living labs and replication labs".

During this phase, the network's activities will focus solely on agroecology in the North African countries hosting the NATAE project's living labs and replication labs: Algeria, Egypt, Morocco, Mauritania and Tunisia. The network will also be looking at activities in the Mediterranean climate zone of South Africa, a country hosting a replication lab, symbolizing the first steps towards expanding the network.

This phase will enable the network to be structured and consolidated on the basis of a limited number of observation sites, but for which the activities and data of the NATAE project will provide a wealth of subjects for exchange.

Phase 2: no earlier than January 2025 and no later than January 2026

"Agroecology in countries around the Mediterranean sharing similar environmental, climatic and socio-economic challenges".

The network's area of interest will be extended to include countries in the agro-climatic zone (southern European and Middle Eastern countries), to cover the entire Mediterranean rim:

- **Mediterranean basin countries in North Africa**

Countries concerned : Algeria, Egypt, Libya, Morocco, Mauritania, Tunisia

Although some regions of these countries are not in Mediterranean climates, but in arid and semi-arid zones, they share similar ecological and socio-economic challenges. What's more, the different agroecosystems of these countries are strongly interlinked. This means that all regions of these countries can be involved in the network's activities.

- **Mediterranean basin countries in Southern Europe**

Countries concerned : Albania, Bosnia, Croatia, Cyprus, France, Greece, Italy, Malta, Montenegro, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, Turkey

The network's activities will concern only those regions of the above-mentioned countries that are affected by drought and aridity, and by the specific features and challenges of Mediterranean agriculture.

So, for example, although France borders the Mediterranean, the MEDAE network will not focus on the northern regions of France, where the challenges are different from those in the Mediterranean (aridity, etc.).

- **Mediterranean basin countries in the Middle East**

Countries concerned: Israel, Jordan, Lebanon, Palestine, Syria,

Phase 3:

A 3^d phase may be envisaged at a later date to extend the network to countries (or regions) outside the Mediterranean basin that share similar agro-environmental conditions and challenges (e.g. California or southern Australia).

**** Key points: OBJECTIVES ****

- The MEDAE network is designed to stimulate collaboration and exchanges between the various stakeholders in Mediterranean agroecology, and to strengthen advocacy of the agroecological transition in the Mediterranean.
- The network focuses on regions of the Mediterranean basin that share common agricultural characteristics (emblematic Mediterranean crops), common environmental constraints (drought, exacerbated climate change, etc.) and similar socio-economic challenges (population growth, urbanization, land pressure, etc.).
- The network will be gradually structured in at least two phases. The MEDAE network will initially focus on agroecology in countries hosting living labs and replication labs (Mauritania, Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Egypt, South Africa). The network's activities will gradually be extended to at least the other countries around the Mediterranean (North Africa, Southern Europe, Middle East).

Chapter 3

Membership

Marion Comptour

Chapter 3 - Membership

Which Mediterranean agro-ecology stakeholders do we want to see represented in the network? Where do they belong geographically? What is the membership procedure?

5. Geographical origin of members

The MEDAE network brings together members who share a common vision of agroecology (Appendix K - Framework document: Shared principles of agroecology) and work towards agroecological transition in the Mediterranean. MEDAE members are not necessarily based in Mediterranean countries, as long as they work in Mediterranean regions.

For example, a Canadian organization working on agroecology in Morocco could be a member of the MEDAE network.

6. Member types

6.1 The importance of a multi-stakeholder network

The MEDAE network's ambition is to include organizations with different statuses and scales of operation, which is necessary to allow a systemic vision of agroecology and to work effectively in favor of the agroecological transition.

Because of its multi-disciplinary and cross-cutting nature, the agro-ecological transition requires action within several spheres of influence (peasantry, development aid, research, public policy, etc.) and on different scales (local, national, regional, international). Exchanges of knowledge, experience sharing and capacity-building between organizations of different kinds and at different levels of action will enable us to gain a collective, cross-sectoral understanding of the challenges of agro-ecological transition, and to act at complementary levels and in complementary roles.

By combining the skills of farmers, research, development organisations, technical institutes, higher education, etc., we will be able to develop agro-ecological innovations adapted to the context, while at the same time speaking with a stronger, unified voice.

The agro-ecological transition is not just about agricultural practices, but about transforming food systems as a whole. Agroecology therefore raises questions about food supply chains, from production to distribution and consumption. The MEDAE network will therefore also be open to stakeholders across food value chains, including food distributors and consumers, in order to understand their aspirations, needs and capacities.

Local authorities and local government institutions also play a key role in the agroecological transition of territories, particularly through land planning and management, support for setting up businesses, the introduction of local agricultural and food policies, help with the development of short distribution channels, etc.

Finally, the MEDAE network recognizes the importance of the expertise of resource persons whose skills and experience in Mediterranean agroecology will enrich the network.

While it is important to be able to involve these different stakeholders in order to envisage localized solutions, it is also essential for an international network, one of whose aims is to advocate, to retain a certain independence from political institutions.

It therefore seems appropriate to distinguish between several MEDAE boards with different rights. These boards, and their associated rights, are described below and detailed in Appendix C. Conditions and rights of membership

6.2 MEDAE members grouped in boards

MEDAE members are essentially **organizations** working on agroecology in the Mediterranean and wishing to become involved in the network's activities. These organisations must have official status. Members are divided into 4 boards:

- **Board A: Technical, educational and research institutes**

This board includes the following organizations: Research institutes, technical institutes, universities and agricultural high schools ...

- **Board B: "Development and experience-sharing organizations**

This board includes the following organizations: Development stakeholders, NGOs, agroecology networks, etc.

- **Board C: Local stakeholders**

This board includes organizations acting on a more local scale: producers' and farmers' organizations, consumer associations, private sectors (distributors, processors, etc.), etc.

- **Board D: Political organizations and individual experts**

This board includes local authorities and governmental and intergovernmental organizations.

It also includes individual experts, who must be sponsored by a member organization.

The steering committee will take care to maintain a balance between the various members, with the participation of organizations (and not individual experts) remaining a priority.

Only members of boards A, B and C can participate in network governance, by electing representatives to the steering committee (see section Steering committee and Appendix C. Conditions and rights of membership).

Because of their institutional and political dimension, Board D members may participate in the network's activities, but will not be involved in its formal governance.

MEDAE members

Figure 3. MEDAE members grouped into boards

6.3 Member representation

Who is a member of the network? Are they organizations, represented by one of their members (legal person), or are they individuals (natural person)?

Network members are **organizations** represented by a focal point. Each organization may also have several participants. The focal point is the network's main contact. He is the link between his organization and the network. His role is specified in Appendix G. Focal point roles

7. Network membership and resignation procedure

7.1 Membership procedure

Organizations wishing to become MEDAE members must :

- Contact the secretariat and fill in an online registration form (Appendix H - MEDAE registration form (online)), including details of :
 - a brief description of the organization and its experience in agroecology
 - interest in the network and desired contribution to the network (including expression of interest in joining a working group)
- Provide a letter of appointment for the focal point
- Confirm to have read (check box) the network framework documents :
 - benefits and commitment of MEDAE members (Appendix I. Framework document: Benefits and commitments of MEDAE members)
 - network operating principles (4/5-page summary of guidelines : Appendix J - Framework document: Network operating principles)
 - shared principles of agroecology (Appendix K - Framework document: Shared principles of agroecology).

Each application will be examined on a case-by-case basis and validated by the MEDAE steering committee.

Individual expert applications must be sponsored by a network member, who will present them to the steering committee.

For the duration of NATAE (until 2026), the steering committee will process membership applications at least twice a year (the periods will be specified on the MEDAE website). Indeed, the network's ambition to reach 70 members by the end of 2026 calls for an active process to attract new members. At the end of the NATAE project, at least one annual meeting of the steering committee will be scheduled to validate membership applications.

Membership renewal

Membership must be renewed at the beginning of each calendar year by all network members. An online form will be available to facilitate renewal.

7.2 Membership fees

Membership of the MEDAE network will be free of charge for the duration of NATAE, as the project will fund the network's activities. At the end of the NATAE project, other sources of funding will have to be found to ensure the network's sustainability, for example through grants, donations, etc. The payment of an annual subscription by all members of the network is also an option envisaged (see section Economic model). The terms of this

contribution will be agreed between members before mid-2026 (amount, adaptation of the amount according to the type of member, payment conditions, etc.).

7.3 Loss of membership

Any member organization may submit its resignation in writing to the network coordinator at any time. Any membership fees due at the time of resignation remain the responsibility of the resigning organization.

An organization or a participant may be removed from the MEDAE network by a resolution adopted at a steering committee meeting. This decision may be taken in the event of a breach of the network's operating principles or ethics (Annexes I and J) or, if a contribution is requested, in the event of voluntary non-payment of the membership fee.

8. Network size and connections to other networks

8.1 Network size: objectives

By the end of the NATAE project in December 2026, the MEDAE network aims to have at least 70 members, of which 20 in Europe and 50 in North Africa, including at least 20 research institutes and 15 NGOs.

Today, the consortium is made up of 22 partners, 10 in Europe and 10 in North Africa, including 12 research institutes and 5 NGOs (Table 1).

	NATAE Consortium	MEDAE targets for 2026
GEOGRAPHY of members		
Europe	10	20
North Africa	10	50
Other (Middle East, South Africa)	2	
TYPE of member		
Universities, research centers and agricultural high schools	12	20
NGOs and associations	5	15
TOTAL	22	70

Table 1. Network size targets

The MEDAE network, initially set up by the NATAE partners, will need to be rapidly extended during the project. This calls for an active process to make the MEDAE network known to organizations likely to be interested, and to motivate them to join. A working group (WG) dedicated to the "recruitment" of new members is planned (see

section 13.1.2.2WG proposals). Some international research and development institutions, recognized worldwide for their expertise in agroecology, have already expressed their interest in joining MEDAE.

8.2 Connection to other networks

The MEDAE network will establish contacts and synergies with other agroecology networks in other regions of Africa and Europe⁶ to promote the sharing of experience and the dissemination of our respective activities.

**** Key points: MEMBERSHIP ****

- Network members are interested in agroecology in the Mediterranean, with no restrictions on their physical location.
- Members are organizations represented by focal points and may have several participants.
- Members can sponsor individual experts who will also be associated with the network.
- MEDAE members are grouped into 4 boards: Board A "Technical, education and research institutes "; Board B "Development and experience-sharing organizations"; Board C "Local stakeholders"; Board D "Political organizations and individual experts".
- Only members of board A, B and C take part in steering and decision-making processes.
- Membership requires endorsement of the network's framework documents (operating principles, shared principles of agroecology, benefits and commitment of members) and the appointment of a focal point.
- The network's ambition to reach 70 members by the end of 2026 requires an active process of 'recruiting' new members.

⁶ For example: Arab Agroecology Network (supported by Terre et Humanisme), Agroecology Europe, Alliance for Agroecology in West Africa...

Chapter 4

Governance

Marion Comptour

Chapter 4 - Governance

Governance refers to the set of measures, rules, decision-making and information bodies that ensure the smooth running of the MEDAE network. The mode of governance also questions the representation of member diversity (types of organization, geographical diversity, etc.) within the network.

9. Host organization

At least for the first few years of the network, MEDAE will have no formal existence. It will be hosted by a host institution.

The host organization provides an administrative and financial manager, responsible for :

- administrative management of the network: reception and follow-up of membership applications, reception and processing of postal mail, reception and processing of e-mails (standard address secretariat@medae.org)
- managing the finances required for network activities (communications, network events, salaried time of the network coordinator and of the administrative and financial manager).

The role of the administrative and financial manager is detailed in Appendix D. Terms of reference: Host organization

The host organization has no representative power in the MEDAE network. It carries no more weight than other organizations in network decision-making.

Please note: The host organization may be different from the organization that carries out the coordination and animation of the network (= coordinating organization, see section below). While responsibility for network coordination may be successively assumed by different MEDAE members, it is desirable for the host organization to remain the same, in order to have a stable postal address. Discussions are underway to ensure this responsibility.

10. Coordinating organization

In all existing networks, animation is identified as a major condition for success. What's more, the questionnaire distributed to the consortium revealed that partners have little time to get actively involved in the network. Thus, the dynamism and durability of the MEDAE network will rely heavily on a network coordinator.

However, a number of points need to be borne in mind, and the position of coordinator raises a number of questions: How do you strike the right balance between providing a stimulating environment for the network but not taking the place of active participation by the members, or hindering their commitment? What management practices and tools can be used to strengthen the collective sense of belonging and encourage exchanges? And how do we finance the post of coordinator?

10.1 Role of the coordinating organization

Thanks to a clearly identified coordinator within the organization, the coordinating organization is in charge of :

- implementation and monitoring of network activities;
- network coordination ;
- the quality of the relationship and exchanges between active members and the steering committee.

An e-mail address dedicated to coordination will be managed by the coordinator (coordination@medae.org).

The coordinator's role is detailed in Appendix E. Terms of reference:

The coordinating organization has no power to represent the MEDAE network. It carries no more weight than other organizations in network decision-making.

10.2 Identification of the coordinating organization

We propose that CARI, which has dedicated funding from the NATAE project, should be the coordinating organization until the end of the NATAE project (December 2026).

Subsequently, an elective process will be organized every 3 years to allow for a possible change in the coordinating institution. However, rotation is not compulsory, and it will be possible for the same institution to carry out several mandates.

The steering committee will first carry out an evaluation of the past mandate with the coordinating organization and will work on the implications of a possible change.

Members (from boards A, B and C only) who wish to do so may then apply to be responsible for coordinating the network. The applications will be examined by the steering committee, which will check that the applicants meet the minimum conditions for coordination and will vote to elect the new coordinating organization. If necessary, a period of training will be provided for the new structure. Ideally, the coordinating organization should alternate between European and North African countries.

The provision of a coordinator by the coordinating structure is, however, dependent on the sources of funding that the network will be able to mobilize at the end of the NATAE project (see section Economic model).

11. Steering committee

11.1 Role of the steering committee

The steering committee monitors activities and ensures they are in line with the network's strategic plan; validates the budget; examines and validates membership applications; and evaluates coordination mandates.

The role of the steering committee is detailed in Appendix F. Terms of reference: Steering Committee

11.2 Composition and election of the steering committee

11.2.1 Composition

Only the **focal points** of members belonging to boards A, B and C (respectively "Technical, education and research institutes" ; "Development and experience-sharing organizations"; and "Local stakeholders" boards) may be elected to the steering committee. Focal points represent their organizations on the steering committee: steering committee membership is organizational, not individual.

The composition of the steering committee aims to ensure a good representation of the types of stakeholders involved, as well as the geographical diversity of the members.

The steering committee will be composed of a maximum* of 3 people per board, ensuring geographical representativeness:

- A representative from Southern Europe
- A representative from North Africa and the Middle East
- A "flexible" representative (Southern Europe, North Africa and Middle East, or other country)

For the sake of parity, each board (when composed of 3 people) must elect at least one female representative to the steering committee.

Maximum*: If a board has fewer than 5 members, it will elect just one representative to the steering committee (among any geographical region listed above). If it has between 5 and 10 members, it will elect 2 representatives from 2 different geographical region. From 15 members per board, 3 representatives will be elected to the steering committee.

Figure 4. Election of the steering committee

11.3 Election of the steering committee

The steering committee will be set up in 2024.

Elections to the steering committee will be held within each A, B and C board. As stated above, each board will elect a maximum of 3 representatives, guaranteeing geographical representativeness and parity.

Each organization will have a single vote (via the focal point) for the election of its representatives to the steering committee.

Elections will be carried out online and administered by the coordinator in each board.

All steering committee candidates must have previously submitted to the coordinator a declaration of candidacy and a statement reflecting their organisation's commitment to support the candidate (if elected) in the performance of his/her duties as a steering committee representative.

The steering committee is elected for three years. After a first term, a representative may be re-elected for a further three-year term.

Pending the formation of the steering committee, decisions will be taken by a restricted interim committee made up of the NATAE coordinating structure (CIHEAM IAMM) and the structure responsible for setting up and running the network (CARI). The advisory board may also be consulted and involved in decision-making.

11.4 Steering committee meetings

Steering committee meetings are held regularly, at least every four months. In most cases, they will be held by videoconference, in English, with French translation provided.

The proposed agenda is prepared by the coordinator 20 days before the meeting and shared with the steering committee for completion and validation.

The validated agenda is sent 15 days before the steering committee meeting to all the focal points of the organizations of boards A, B and C. Whenever relevant, the steering committee representatives will gather the opinions of the members of their board (by e-mail, or by organizing a dedicated meeting).

Depending on the session's agenda, other people may be invited to take part in the steering committee meeting (for example, a representative of a working group, or the administrative and financial manager for budget items). The CIHEAM IAMM, coordinator of the NATAE project, will be a permanent guest at the steering committee for the duration of the project.

Steering committee meetings are coordinated by the coordinator, who provides logistical and administrative support.

Steering committee decisions are taken by consensus, but when this is not possible, a vote is held. In the event of a vote, decisions are taken by simple majority. The steering committee decision quorum is made up of at least half the steering committee representatives (5 representatives out of 9).

At each steering committee meeting, a secretary is appointed to draft the minutes. The minutes are sent for completion and validation to the steering committee in the week following the meeting, then distributed to network members (board A, B, C only) by the coordinator.

Figure 5. Organization of a steering committee

12. Annual network meetings

Once a year, a meeting is organized with all MEDAE members. This meeting provides an opportunity to review the previous year's activities, and to share results and information about MEDAE (Steering committee decisions, budget, activities). It will also provide an opportunity to share the strategic vision for the coming year and planned activities.

This annual meeting will be a key opportunity to consolidate the network's internal dynamics.

Ideally, the annual meeting can be organized face-to-face, combined with another network event (face-to-face webinar, for example), but it can also be held remotely.

**** Key points: GOVERNANCE ****

- The network is hosted by a long-term host organization, responsible for its administrative and financial management.
- A coordinating organization (which may rotate every 3 years) will be in charge of leading and coordinating the network's activities.
- The steering committee is elected for 3 years. It is made up of a maximum of 3 representatives per board (A, B and C), to ensure a good representation of the types and the geographical diversity of members.
- Network decisions are taken by the steering committee, which meets at least every 4 months.
- An annual meeting will be organized with all members to review the past year's activities and present the strategy for the coming year.

Chapter 5

Activities and communication

Marion Comptour

Chapter 5 - Activities, communication, economic model

What activities do we want to carry out within the network, and how should we organize ourselves to carry them out? How can we communicate about our activities, both internally and externally? What economic model will ensure the long-term future of the network's activities?

13. Activities

The MEDAE network was officially launched on July 4th, 2023. Several activities will follow, in particular a series of webinars between September and December 2023 to discuss agroecology in different types of North African agroecosystems.

In January 2024, the host and coordination organizations will be officially validated, along with the guidelines. An action plan for 2024 will be presented.

Some network activities may be organized at the initiative of working groups (see section below), but other cross-functional activities will be organized and led by the CARI coordinator.

13.1 Working groups

13.1.1 Role of the working groups

Working groups bring together MEDAE members interested in contributing to a specific area of interest.

These working groups pool knowledge and expertise to organize activities (e.g. webinars) or produce documents (e.g. position papers). Working groups are designed to produce results and are organized around a specific project. As such, they are periodic and evolving: they are created for a specific project, and come to an end once the work has been completed.

13.1.2 Organization and creation of working groups (WG)

13.1.2.1 Organization

Each working group will determine its own internal modus operandi (regularity of meetings, decision-making procedures, etc.). Working groups may decide to organize themselves into sub-groups (e.g. by region, by type of agroecosystem, etc.).

However, a responsible person must be chosen from each working group. This person should belong to the A, B or C boards. He or she must report regularly to the coordinator on progress and the budget (needs, expenses) dedicated to his or her WG. He/she may be invited to certain steering committee meetings to report on the progress, problems, issues, etc. of his/her working group.

13.1.2.2 WG proposals

Setting up working groups will depend on members' motivations, needs and opportunities. Only issues that cut across several types of members and several countries in the network, and are likely to lead to concrete achievements or proposals, will justify the creation of working groups.

While it may be appropriate for certain categories of members to group together (by type, by country...) to exchange and collaborate, this does not constitute a network working group in the strict sense of the term.

We therefore differentiate between :

- Exchange groups that are very specific, or involve only a few members or a single type of member. They enable members to collaborate and exchange ideas on very specific tasks. Unofficial, these groups are not binding on the steering committee or the network coordinator. There will be no communication within the network about these groups.
- Working groups validated by the steering committee. These WGs will mobilize a diversity of member organizations and countries. They will be created around a common theme, with a view to achieving concrete terminations. These WGs will be able to call on the network coordinator, at least from time to time. MEDAE's various communication media will be used to publicize the creation and progress of WGs.

During the first two years of the project, at least two formal working groups are required:

- **Membership Working Group :**

It is important to set up this working group at the start of the network to validate membership processes and membership framework documents :

- Benefits and commitments of MEDAE members (Appendix I. Framework document: Benefits and commitments of MEDAE members)
- Operating principles of the network (Appendix J - Framework document: Network operating principles)
- Shared principles of agroecology (Appendix K - Framework document: Shared principles of agroecology).

This group will also reflect on a strategy to accelerate the accession of new members in order to meet the objectives of the NATAE project.

- **Advocacy working group**

This working group responds to MEDAE objective 3: "To represent Mediterranean agroecology stakeholders at international level and develop political and scientific advocacy in favor of agroecology". During the years of the NATAE project, it will notably enable work on deliverables D6.1 (Political advocacy files) and D6.4 (Policy paper on agroecology in North African countries) and on task T6.5 (organization of political conferences). It will enable us to contextualize advocacy in response to the issues identified in each region, identify advocacy targets and reflect on advocacy strategies and discourse for each target.

Other working groups may be set up at a later date:

- **Communication working group (internal and external)**

This group will reflect on internal (mail list, cloud for document sharing...) and external communications strategies (logos, website, graphic charter...) (see section below).

- **Working group to share knowledge and practices**

This working group responds to Objective 2 "Promote the exchange of information, knowledge, solutions and experience between network members". This working group will promote the pooling of knowledge and its dissemination within the network.

- **Financing working group**

It may be appropriate to create a "financing" working group to reflect on MEDAE's future economic model (see section Economic model).

14. Communication

A future working group will consider the challenges and tools of internal and external communication for MEDAE. However, certain proposals can already be made.

14.1 Internal communications

Internal communication concerns communication within the network: between members, between members and the steering committee, etc.

To facilitate exchanges and enable optimal communication, we advise:

14.1.1 Language in the network

As MEDAE is an international network, the two languages used for internal communication within the network will be French and English.

Although Arabic is widely spoken by network members, meetings and exchanges within the network cannot be conducted in Arabic, as this would effectively exclude some non-Arabic-speaking members.

14.1.2 Mailing lists

Several mail lists will be created to facilitate exchanges:

- Mail list "focal points": grouping together the focal points of all members
- Mail list "boards A, B, C": grouping the focal points of the member organizations of boards A,B,C

- Mail list "all members": including focal points and participants from all members
- Mail list "workgroup" : one mail list by WG
- Mail list steering committee
- ...

14.1.3 Sharing platform

An internal sharing tool (documents, information) will be set up. We need to think about what form this tool will take: cloud, internal platform?

14.2 External communications

External communications help to promote the network and its products to the outside world.

14.2.1 Media

- **Website**: a website, linked to the NATAE project website, will be dedicated to the MEDAE network.

The website will feature at least :

- The objectives of the MEDAE network
 - The values (shared principles) of the MEDAE network
 - A list of members and governance
 - A list and objectives of working groups
 - Membership terms and conditions
 - News and updates will be published regularly.
 - Secretariat contact
- **Social networks**: the MEDAE network will have at least one facebook page

14.2.2 Graphic charter

The Communications WG will have to think about a graphic charter (including a "MEDAE" logo) and will specify the conditions of use of graphic supports.

15. Economic model

In all networks, the question arises of the economic model and the balance between the network's various resources (member contributions, external public or private funding, etc.).

Under MEDAE, the NATAE project will provide funding for the network's first few years, but this funding is inherently temporary. By the end of 2026, when NATAE comes to an end, the MEDAE network will need to have found new sources of funding to ensure the sustainability of its activities and associated functions (coordinator, administrative and financial manager).

As mentioned above, a "financing" working group could be set up to consider MEDAE's future economic model.

Here are some possible sources of financing:

- Membership fees

As mentioned in the Membership fees it is envisaged that members will contribute financially to the network, via an annual membership fee, introduced at the end of the NATAE project. The fee would be adapted to the type of member.

- Network project grants

Once the network has been set up, it will be possible to set up projects under the umbrella of the network and apply for external funding, particularly multilateral funding, which each member would not have been able to access on its own. It should be noted that donors often fund the network itself less than the joint programs run by network members.

- Co-financing of network members' activities

Within the framework of projects led by certain members, activities can be opened up and communicated to the whole network. These activities are financed by the members' projects, but benefit the network and contribute to its vitality (webinars, exchange days, etc.).

**** Key points: ACTIVITIES, COMMUNICATION, FUNDING ****

- Some activities will be organised at the initiative of the working groups and other cross-cutting activities will be organised by the coordinator.
- A minimum of two working groups will be set up in the first year: Membership WG and Advocacy WG. Other WGs may be set up: communication, exchange of practices, funding.
- The network will communicate in French and English.
- The network should have found sources of funding by the end of the NATAE project in 2026. Membership fees are one possible contribution.

Appendices

Appendices

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Appendix A. Questionnaire submitted to the network

Note: Some responses to the questionnaire are given in orange boxes. Qualitative comments are not reported here to respect the anonymity of the questionnaire

A few words about the MEDAE network as described in the project document

The MEDAE network (MEDiterranean multi-actor network on AgroEcology) will accompany NATAE's conceptual and methodological work, and discuss the results obtained to pave the way for policy-makers and developers. By bringing together representatives from different scales and types of institutions (administration, education, research, development, extension), the MEDAE network aims to bridge the gap between local, national and international contexts, policies and knowledge. The MEDAE network will act as a knowledge transfer gas pedal. Its aim is to help stakeholders, both within and outside the project, to acquire and share knowledge-based solutions and information.

MEDAE will be made up of the consortium members, then gradually extended to other members interested in the development of agroecology in the Mediterranean. By the end of the project, MEDAE will comprise at least 20 members in Europe (including EU Mediterranean countries), and at least 50 members in North Africa, including 20 research partners and 15 NGOs. The MEDAE network will be closely linked to agroecology knowledge communities in other parts of Africa and Europe.

MEDAE will be designed to be sustainable after the end of the project.

Why a questionnaire?

These elements of the network's description in the project document are not definitive, and can (and will) be rediscussed. The network is to be co-constructed according to our desires, expectations, objectives and means. The purpose of this questionnaire is to gather your expectations of the MEDAE network in terms of objectives, composition and governance. The responses will be analyzed by CARI and discussed together at the MEDAE launch meeting in early July. They will serve as a basis for drafting the MEDAE network guidelines (D5.2 delivered in M12-December 2023).

Network experience

1. Are you or your organization part of an agroecology network?

If Yes:

- What is/are this/these network(s) (*Name the network and add the website if applicable*)
- For what purpose(s) are you a member of this/these network(s)? What's in it for you?
- How are you personally involved in these networks, and what is your role?
- What do you see as the strengths of these networks?
- And their weakness?

If No :

For what reason(s) (*e.g. you don't have enough time to get involved in a network, you don't know of any existing agro-ecology networks that match your objectives, etc.*)?

MEDAE objectives

2. A network can meet several objectives. What are your expectations of the MEDAE network?

Please tick the 3 objectives that you consider to be priorities for MEDAE

- Stimulate collaborations and projects between the various stakeholders acting to develop agroecology in North Africa.
- Strengthening the capacities of network members
- Exchange information and knowledge between network members (agroecological practices, scientific articles or non-scientific publications, funding opportunities...).
- Communicating and disseminating the results of the NATAE project to a wider community

- Represent Mediterranean agroecology stakeholders at international level and develop political advocacy in favor of agroecology.
- Increase fundraising, access larger donors
- Other (please specify)

3. Please explain, for the objective that seems most important to you, what it means in particular to you, and the concrete actions the network can put in place to achieve it.

Example: "Exchange information" --> As a farmer, this objective could mean exchanging with other producers on agroecological practices. This could take the form of video testimonials or the creation of an exchange forum.

4. For you, the MEDAE network (Mediterranean network on agro-ecology) should focus on

Only one possible answer

- Agroecology practiced in North African countries only (the countries hosting Living labs in the NATAE project).
- Agroecology practiced in all Mediterranean countries, including EU Mediterranean countries* (what we mean more specifically by countries Mediterranean will have to be defined together)
- No opinion yet

Possible comment:

Membership

5. In your opinion, do MEDAE members :

Only one possible answer.

- Must be based in Mediterranean countries (in the EU and Africa).
- Can be located outside the Mediterranean region if they work on agroecology in Mediterranean countries (for example, a Canadian researcher working on agroecology in Morocco).
- No opinion yet

Possible comment:

6. Is there a stakeholder in the list below that you would NOT like to see represented in the MEDAE community?

Several answers are possible.

- Research institutes
- Universities / agricultural schools
- Development actors and NGOs
- Producer and farmer organizations
- Consumer associations
- Agroecology promotion networks
- Government institutions
- Political decision-makers
- Private sector
- Citizens interested in agroecology
- NO (the entire list can be represented)
- Other (please specify)

Possible comment:

7. In your opinion, can MEDAE members be

Several answers are possible.

- Individuals
- Representatives of organizations and institutions (legal entities)

8. In your opinion, if institutions are members of MEDAE, does this risk hindering freedom of expression and opinion in advocacy?

- Yes
- No
- No opinion yet

Possible comment:

9. How do you think network members could be represented on the steering committee?

For example, 1 member per country and/or 1 member per type of institution

Commitment

10. On a scale of 1 to 5, how would you rate the relevance of the creation of MEDAE for your future activities?

1 = not very relevant; and 5 = extremely valuable to my business

1 2 3 4 5

11. On a scale of 1 to 5, how would you rate the time you have available to contribute to MEDAE activities?

1 = very little time, a few hours a year; and 5 = I am very available, a few hours a week.

1 2 3 4 5

Identity

12. Please specify your name and the name of your organization

Appendix B. Preliminary scenario discussions

Scenario MEDAE		Questions
Objectives	Proposition (scenario)	
1	Zone of interest of the network will encompass (see map if needed) - Southern Europe countries (Mediterranean climate) (<i>Portugal, Spain, France, Italy, Slovenia, Bosnia, Croatia, Montenegro, Albania, Greece, Malta, Turkey</i>) - North African countries (Mediterranean climates and other) (<i>Mauritania, Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Egypt, Lybia</i>) -Middle East countries (<i>Lebanon</i>)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For Southern Europe countries : do you agree that we will specifically look at the mediterranean zones of those countries ? (ex only southern France) For North African Countries : do you agree that our interest will concern the whole countries even if some areas do not have a Mediterranean climate (e.g. deserts). Countries of interest are CHEAM countries + Slovenia, Bosnia, Croatia, Montenegro, Mauritania and Lybia. Do you agree to exclude Syria and Israel ?
Activities and fundings	2 Working groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do you agree on these two working groups for the first two years of the network ? Do you have other ideas / interet for other working groups that should be set up as soon as the network is up and running?
Membership	3 Geographical origin of members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do you agree ? Or are we closing the network to organisations from outside Europe and North africa?
	4 Type of stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do you agree to exclude governmental institutions (ex ministry, agricultural services department, forestry department...) Do we set up criteria to accept or reject members? Which ones ? (ex safeguards for private sector) Do we include local communities ?
	5 Membership process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do you agree ? What do you think of the proposition to have a disclaimer for advocacy documents or to only include the logos of the organisations validating the document ? (Can limit the reluctance of organizations to integrate the network)
	6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Brainstorming : Do you have any ideas for other important documents that new members should validate to confirm their membership of the network and their commitment?
	7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do you agree on a paid membership after the NATAE project ? Do you agree that the membership fee will be adapted to member types ?
Governance	8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do you agree ?
	9 Network formality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do you agree that the hosting institution CAN change, but that it is not mandatory ?
	10 Steering comitty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do you agree to regroup stakeholders in these 3 boards ? Do you agree to have geographical represents in each board ? (south europe, north africa, other regions)

Appendix C. Conditions and rights of membership

The MEDAE network is made up of various organizations (and individual experts) divided into 4 boards.

It is also possible for people from outside the network to benefit from certain network activities.

The table below describes the conditions for joining the network and the implications for each member.

	Board members A, B, C	Board members D	External person
Status	Organizations (from list 1), represented by a focal point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organizations (from list 2), represented by a focal point Individual experts, not affiliated with organizations but recognized as resource persons 	Not part of the network
Conditions for joining the network	<u>For organizations</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fill in an online registration form Approve network framework documents Identifying a focal point Have your application validated by the steering committee Pay membership fees, if any 		
		<u>For individual experts</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recognized expertise in agro-ecology, enabling active participation in network activities Be sponsored (recommendation letter) by a member organization 	
Provides feedback on the network's framework and statutory documents	√ Only NATAE consortium members for now, but all members when the guidelines are revised in 2025)		
Can participate in working groups	√	√	
May be responsible for a work group	√		
Receives information related to network decision-making (e.g. steering committee minutes)	√		
Receives private information within the	√	√	

network about its activities			
Receives public information (newsletter, website)	√	√	√
May take part in internal network events (meetings, etc.).	√	√	
May participate in network public events (webinars, etc.)	√	√	√

List 1:

Research institutes, technical institutes, universities and agronomic high schools, development stakeholders, NGOs, agroecology stakeholder networks, producer and farmer organizations, consumer associations, private sector (distributors, processors, etc.), etc.

List 2:

Local authorities, Governmental and intergovernmental organizations, Individual experts.

Appendix D. Terms of reference: Host organization

The host organization provides an administrative and financial manager in charge of :

- **Administrative management of the network :**

- Reception and processing of postal mail and e-mails (e.g. secretariat@medae.org).
- Receipt and follow-up of membership applications
- Monitoring and updating the list of members and their contacts

- **Managing the finances required for network activities**

- Proposal and design of monitoring and financial reporting tools
- Management and monitoring of finances required for network activities, including communications, network events, salaried time of the network coordinator and administrative and financial manager.
- Financial report produced every 3 months (made available to the coordinator and steering committee).
- Contribute to the mobilization of funding to carry out the activities set out in the action plan, including the management (if necessary) of memberships.
- If necessary, contact the landlords

- **Administrative and financial reporting to the steering committee**

The administrative and financial manager may be invited to certain steering committee meetings to share administrative and budgetary information.

The steering committee must ensure that sufficient resources are made available to the managing organization to enable it to fulfill its administrative and financial responsibilities.

Appendix E. Terms of reference: Coordinating organization

With a clearly identified coordinator, the coordinating organization will have to meet the following main objectives: ensure that network activities are carried out properly, establish and nurture a network dynamic, promote the dissemination of information and decisions within the network, and guarantee the network's sustainability.

An e-mail address dedicated to coordination will be managed by the coordinator (animation@medae.org).

The tasks of the coordinator will be as follows:

- **Setting up the network and planning activities**

- Design, with the help of the membership working group, and subject to validation by the steering committee, of the network's operating documents and tools:

- Network framework documents (network operating principles, shared agro-ecology principles)
- The action plan: a 3-year action plan in line with strategic objectives, and a more precise annual action plan.
- Communication tools

- Contribute to and monitor the implementation of the network's action plan by :

- Programming activities (excluding workgroups)
- Supporting working groups (WGs) in carrying out their activities

- **Implementing and monitoring activities**

- Programming activities in line with the action plan

- Monitoring WG activities :

- Regular contact with WG leaders (agree with leaders on frequency of contact): discussions on content, funding and organization of each activity.
- Participates in certain working group meetings.
- Review and validation of the ToR for each WG activity
Where applicable: contribution to the design, organization and running of activities
- Budget review and monitoring: Verification of funding requests by working groups for the implementation of activities
- Contribution to the mobilization, in conjunction with the administrative and financial manager, of the co-financing required to carry out activities
- Distribution of WG meeting minutes (drafted by the WG) to other members

- Activity reporting

- Proposed model for periodic reporting of activities by WGs
- Receipt and validation of narrative reports and activity deliverables submitted by WGs
- Indicator tracking

- **Coordination**

- Steering committee coordination and communication between steering committee and members

- Preparing the agenda
- Participation in steering committee, logistical and administrative support for meetings
- Report on the steering committee decisions: sharing the minutes with members of boards A, B and C:

- Coordination of annual network meetings

- **Internal and external communications**

- Ensures smooth internal communication within the network via mail list and dedicated communication tools
- Ensures external communication: website and Facebook updates

- **Tasks relating to network strategy and representation**

- Contribute to strategic intelligence on topics and frameworks related to Mediterranean agroecology
- Helping to ensure the network's representativeness and positions

The steering committee must ensure that sufficient resources are made available to the coordinating organization to enable it to fulfill its missions. It is recommended that the coordinator be dedicated to the network for the equivalent of half-time.

Appendix F. Terms of reference: Steering Committee

The steering committee monitors activities and ensures they are in line with the network's strategic plan; validates the budget; examines and validates membership applications; and evaluates coordination mandates.

- **Strategic network vision**

- Develops a strategic plan for the network
- Contributes to the development of the network's action plan, checks that it is consistent with the network's strategic plan, and validates the action plan (a 3-year action plan and an annual action plan).
- Contributes to and validates network framework documents: network operating principles, shared agro-ecology principles, etc.
- Examines partnership strategy options and priority links with other initiatives on the subject.

- **Activity monitoring and decision-making**

- Monitors the progress of the action plan according to agreed objectives, on schedule and within budget.
- Discusses and validates any internal changes to the action plan, readjusts priorities in the event of difficulties, warns of malfunctions.
- Makes decisions, by vote, on network operations

Budget

- Approves the budget.

Memberships

- Examines and validates new membership applications.
- Decides, where applicable, on the amount of membership fees for the various structures.

Appendix G. Focal point roles

Focal points represent their organization within the network.

- The focal point is the network's key contact. They act as a link between their organization (and participants) and the network.
- The focal point forwards network decisions to his or her organization, and ensures that his or her organization validates the production of certain documents (advocacy documents, decisions involving the organization's finances, etc.).
- The focal point can be elected to the steering committee
- The focal point is responsible for updating his organization's annual list of participants.

Appendix H - MEDAE registration form (online)

Will be available both in French and English

Name of Organization			
Date of Establishment			
Address of principal office			City:
			Country:
Telephone	Country code:	City code:	Number:
Website:			
Purpose of Organization			
Country/ies in which organization is active			
Organization Type (Please check only one) <input type="checkbox"/> Academic, Technical or Research Institution <input type="checkbox"/> Non-Governmental Organization (NGO) <input type="checkbox"/> Network in Agroecology <input type="checkbox"/> Producer/farmer organization <input type="checkbox"/> Consumer organization <input type="checkbox"/> Private sector <input type="checkbox"/> Local authorities <input type="checkbox"/> Decentralized governmental institution. <input type="checkbox"/> International organization <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify:		Geographic Scope: <input type="checkbox"/> Local <input type="checkbox"/> National <input type="checkbox"/> Regional (e.g. Mediterranean) <input type="checkbox"/> Global	
Brief profile (maximum 8 lines)			
Please describe your experience (achievements) relating to agroecological issues and practices. (maximum 15 lines)			
Please describe your interest in the MEDAE network, how you would like to participate in MEDAE activities.			
Which working group(s) you would be interested to participate in?			

<input type="checkbox"/> Membership	
<input type="checkbox"/> Advocacy	
<input type="checkbox"/> Communication	
<input type="checkbox"/> Funding	
<input type="checkbox"/> Exchange, knowledge sharing	
<input type="checkbox"/> Other	
Name and contact of the focal point Join a nomination letter	Name: Email: Phone No.:
I certify that I have read the MEDAE network framework documents and approve them : <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Benefits and commitment of being a MEDAE member <input type="checkbox"/>- Operating principles <input type="checkbox"/>- Shared principles of agroecology <input type="checkbox"/>	
Date of Submission:	

Appendix I. Framework document: Benefits and commitments of MEDAE members

This document is a framework document for the network. It summarises the benefits and commitments to be a MEDAE member.

It will be published on the MEDAE network website and must be consulted and approved by members wishing to join.

This document is a provisional version which will have to be approved by the membership working group.

MEDAE is a multi-actor network promoting agroecological transition in the Mediterranean.

Benefits

By becoming a MEDAE member, your organization will be able to :

1. Work as a multi-disciplinary, multiple-horizon team and collaborate more synergistically to promote agroecology in the Mediterranean. The network offers the opportunity to collaborate with members with similar interests, as well as with members with specific expertise that your organization lacks, or whose expertise are complementary.
2. Exchange information, knowledge, practices, experiences, know-how and co-construct knowledge with different stakeholders in Mediterranean agro-ecology who share similar issues.
3. Access capacity-building opportunities through direct exchanges between members
4. Participate in projects developed by the network or by network member organizations. Project proposals associated with this type of network are more likely to secure funding.
5. Participate in joint advocacy actions in favor of agroecology
6. Gain visibility and be able to increase your organization's influence in national and international policy dialogues through coordination and partnership, creating a stronger, unified and recognized voice for agroecology.
7. Strengthen your online presence with the MEDAE website, enabling your organization to promote its work.
8. Access information. Your organization will receive MEDAE communications about important events, webinars, exchange times, publications, and funding opportunities.

Commitment

1. Members undertake to comply with the network operating principles described in Appendix J - Framework document: Network operating principles

2. The network promotes universal human values such as respect, openness, empathy, solidarity and benevolence. The network has no political or religious affiliations. Each member must respect these values and principles, and act in a spirit of sharing and respectful collaboration with all network members.
3. Members contribute actively to the network's activities and dynamism, and in particular to the sharing of information at all levels.
4. Members are invited to participate in working groups.
5. Members agree to attend annual meetings.
6. Members of boards A, B and C take part in the election of the steering committee and the drafting of certain framework documents.

Appendix J - Framework document: Network operating principles

This document is a framework document for the network. It summarises the most important points in the network's operation that members need to be aware of. It will be published on the MEDAE network website and must be consulted and approved by members wishing to join.

This document is a provisional version which will have to be approved by the membership working group.

History

The MEDAE network emerged as part of the [NATAE](#) project (Fostering the Agroecological Transition in North Africa [2022-2026]) and from the desire of the project partners to create a sustainable network for exchanges between the various stakeholders involved in promoting the agroecological transition in the Mediterranean. The network's operating principles were developed through a collaborative process with the various NATAE project partners.

Objectives

The MEDE network has three main objectives:

- Stimulating collaboration and projects between the various stakeholders working to develop agroecology in the Mediterranean
- To promote the exchange of information, knowledge, solutions and experience between network members
- To represent agroecology stakeholders in the Mediterranean at international level and develop political advocacy in favour of agroecology.

The network focuses on regions of the Mediterranean basin that share common agricultural characteristics and face similar environmental constraints (drought, exacerbated climate change, etc.) and socio-economic challenges (population growth, urbanisation, land pressure, etc.).

The network will be structured progressively in at least two phases. MEDAE will first concentrate its activities in the countries hosting field laboratories in the NATAE project (Mauritania, Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Egypt, South Africa). Activities will then be extended to at least the other countries around the Mediterranean (North Africa, Southern Europe, Middle East).

Membership

The MEDAE network aims to be made up of organizations with different statuses and operating at different levels, in order to encourage the exchange of knowledge and experience and to gain a collective and systemic understanding of how to work effectively to promote the agro-ecological transition.

MEDAE members are essentially organizations that will be represented by a focal point, the network's main contact.

Members are grouped into 4 boards:

- **Board A: Technical, teaching and research institutes**

Made up of research institutes, technical institutes, universities and agricultural high schools ...

- **Board B: "Development and experience-sharing organisations".**

Made up of development stakeholders, NGOs, networks of agro-ecology stakeholders, etc.

- **Board C: Local stakeholders**

This board includes organizations operating at a more local level: producers' and farmers' organisations, consumer associations, private sectors (distributors, processors, etc.), etc.

- **Board D: Political organisations and individual experts**

This board includes local and regional authorities and governmental and intergovernmental organizations. It also includes individual experts, recognized by the MEDAE network as resource persons. To join the network, individual experts must be sponsored by a member organization.

For more details on the conditions and rights of the various members, see Appendix 1.

Governance

The MEDAE network is governed and run by its members.

At least for the first few years, the MEDAE network will not have a formal existence. It will be hosted by a host organization that is itself a member of the network. The host organization will also be responsible for the administrative and financial management of the network.

The MEDAE network will be coordinated by a coordinating organization, possibly rotating every 3 years, responsible for implementing and monitoring the network's activities.

A steering committee, responsible for monitoring the network's activities and decision-making, will be elected for 3 years. It will be made up of a maximum of 3 representatives per board A, B and C (elected from among the focal points of the organizations), and will have to guarantee the geographical representativeness of the members as well as parity. Because of their institutional and political dimension, the members of board D will not be able to participate in the formal governance of the network.

An annual meeting will be held with all members to review the past year's activities and present the strategy for the coming year.

Activities

A network action plan will be implemented in 2024.

Some of the network's activities will be organised by working groups, bringing together network members interested in contributing in a specific area of interest. The working groups are designed to produce results, and are organised around a specific project (organization of webinars, production of advocacy, etc.). They are therefore periodic and evolving: they are set up for a specific project and come to an end once the work has been completed.

During the first two years of the project, at least two formal working groups will be set up: A membership working group and an advocacy working group. Other working groups may be set up at a later stage: a communication working group, a knowledge-sharing working group and a funding working group.

A person in charge (from boards A, B or C) must be chosen from each working group to liaise with the coordinator.

Financing

Membership of the MEDAE network will be free for the duration of the NATAE project. At the end of the NATAE project, sources of funding will have to be found to ensure the sustainability of the network's activities and associated functions (coordinator, administrative and financial manager). The search for subsidies and donations, as well as the payment of an annual subscription by network members, are options being considered.

Languages

The two languages used for internal communication within the network will be French and English.

Join the network

To join the network, members will need to complete an online registration form, approve the network's framework documents⁷ and nominate a focal point by providing a letter of appointment.

Each application for membership will be examined on a case-by-case basis and validated by the MEDAE steering committee.

Membership renewal

All members of the network will have to renew their membership at the beginning of each calendar year. An online form will be available to members to make it easier for them to renew their commitment.

Loss of membership

Any member organization may submit its resignation in writing to the network coordinator at any time. Any membership fees due at the time of resignation will remain the responsibility of the resigning organization.

An organization or a participant may be removed from the MEDAE network by a resolution adopted at a steering committee meeting. This decision may be taken in the event of a breach of the network's operating principles or ethics or, if a membership fee is charged, in the event of voluntary non-payment of the fee.

Appendices

Conditions and rights of membership (see Appendix C of the guidelines)

⁷ The network's framework documents are Network Operating Principles, Shared Principles of Agroecology, and Member Benefits and Commitment.

Appendix K - Framework document: Shared principles of agroecology

This document is a framework document for the network. It will present the shared principles of the network's agroecology. It will be published on the MEDAE network website and must be consulted and approved by members wishing to join.

This document will be drawn up by the membership working group.

NATAE

North African Transition
to AgroEcology

www.natae-agroecology.eu

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